

ROLE OF SCHOOL CULTURE IN SHAPING MORAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

The study examined the role of school culture in shaping moral behaviour among primary schools in Osun State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, where five research questions were raised to guide the study. The population of the study consisted of all primary schools in Osun State. The target population comprised primary school teachers, where 500 teachers were selected across the 3 Senatorial Districts in the State, using a simple random sampling technique. The Role of School Culture in Shaping Moral Behaviour Questionnaire (RSCMBQ) was developed to obtain valid information from the participants. Content validity was conducted by two experts in Primary Education and Educational Psychology, while the reliability of the instrument was carried out with the use of Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Estimate, which yielded an index value of 0.88. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The findings revealed that the most common forms of school culture practiced in primary schools are setting of clear rules and routines to promote discipline and respect, and promotion of inclusiveness and respect for diversity within the classroom. Also, school culture influences the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State. It was recommended that school management should encourage teachers and school leaders to consistently model positive moral behaviour, should integrate character and moral education into daily classroom instruction across subjects, and strengthen collaboration between schools and parents to ensure consistent moral guidance at home and school.

Keywords: School Culture, Moral Behaviour, Moral Values,

Introduction

School culture serves as a powerful influence on the moral development of primary school pupils. It encompasses the values, norms, relationships, and practices that shape daily life within the school environment. During the formative years of primary education, children are highly impressionable and learn not only from formal instruction but also from the social and moral cues embedded in their surroundings. A positive school culture, one that promotes respect, fairness, empathy, and responsibility, creates a fertile ground for nurturing moral behaviour in young learners (Deal & Peterson, 2016). Through interactions with teachers, peers, and institutional routines, pupils begin to internalize ethical standards that guide their actions within and beyond the school setting.

School culture is widely recognized as a powerful force in shaping the academic, social, and moral development of pupils. It refers to the collective values, beliefs, attitudes, norms, and practices that define the everyday experiences within a school community. In recent years, educational research has increasingly emphasized the central role of school culture in fostering inclusive, supportive, and high-performing learning environments, especially during the early years of schooling, when pupils are most impressionable (Jain, 2021). A positive school culture promotes safety, belonging, and shared purpose. In primary schools, where children are developing their identities and social skills, such a culture lays the foundation for emotional and psychological stability. According to Thapa et al. (2023), a supportive school climate, characterized by respectful relationships, emotional safety, and

collaborative learning, enhances pupils' engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. When pupils feel that they are part of a nurturing school community, they are more likely to develop confidence, empathy, and resilience.

In schools where leaders visibly embody the values they promote, such as integrity, fairness, and respect, teachers and pupils are more likely to mirror these traits in their daily interactions. In addition, fostering a culture of inclusion and equity has become increasingly important in the post-COVID educational landscape. According to Okoye and Nwachukwu (2021), schools that prioritize inclusive practices, such as differentiated instruction, support for children with disabilities, and gender-sensitive policies, build a more democratic and empathetic culture. These efforts ensure that every child feels valued, respected, and empowered to participate fully in school life, regardless of background or ability.

Furthermore, the integration of social and emotional learning into school culture has proven beneficial. Social and emotional learning programs promote self-awareness, empathy, and responsible decision-making, skills essential for moral behavior and academic success. A growing body of literature supports the idea that SEL, when embedded within the daily culture of primary schools, enhances not only pupil well-being but also teacher satisfaction and school cohesion (Jones et al., 2020). When schools actively collaborate with families through communication, joint activities, and inclusive decision-making, they create consistency between home and school expectations. School-wide practices and traditions also shape the moral and social fabric of primary schools. Assemblies, class responsibilities, storytelling sessions, and peer mentoring programs are all cultural tools that

schools use to instill values. Narvaez et al. (2020) assert that these rituals reinforce moral development when they are consistent, inclusive, and reflective of the community's shared values. For example, weekly storytelling activities centered on themes like honesty, kindness, and courage can help young children internalize moral lessons in relatable and engaging ways.

Moral behaviour among primary school pupils refers to the demonstration of ethical values such as honesty, respect, responsibility, empathy, and fairness in everyday interactions and decision-making. At this stage of development, children are beginning to form a sense of right and wrong, influenced significantly by their environment, especially family, school, and peers. Primary school represents a critical period during which moral habits and foundational ethical reasoning are established (Narvaez et al., 2020). One of the defining features of moral behaviour in early childhood is its reliance on adult modeling and reinforcement. Pupils often imitate the actions of adults they trust, especially parents and teachers. When these adults demonstrate honesty, fairness, and care in their actions, children internalize these values through observation and social learning (Osakwe & Edeh, 2022). Egwuonwu and Egwuonwu and Obasi (2022) revealed that pupils exposed to regular moral instruction and who observed ethical conduct by their teachers were more likely to show respect for rules, cooperate with peers, and demonstrate empathy.

In the classroom context, moral behaviour is often reflected in how pupils respond to rules, handle conflicts, and relate with others. For instance, pupils who consistently wait their turn, help their peers, report truthfully, or apologize for wrongdoing are exhibiting early forms of moral reasoning and ethical decision-making. These behaviours are not innate but

nurtured through structured guidance, routine moral discussions, and value-laden activities embedded within the school culture (Narvaez, 2021). The integration of social and emotional learning (SEL) into the primary curriculum has been identified as a powerful tool for fostering moral competencies. SEL promotes self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, and responsible decision-making, attributes that underpin moral behaviour (Jones et al., 2020).

Peer relationships also play a critical role in shaping moral conduct among primary school pupils. Children begin to navigate fairness, justice, and loyalty within their friendships. When teachers create a classroom culture of inclusivity and respect, pupils are more likely to demonstrate positive moral behaviours such as sharing, defending peers against bullying, and resolving disagreements peacefully (Thapa et al., 2023). Moreover, cooperative learning settings, peer mediation programs, and classroom responsibilities help pupils develop a sense of moral duty toward their community. The digital age has also introduced new dimensions to moral behaviour among pupils. With increasing access to mobile devices and the internet, even primary school pupils are exposed to complex social issues and online interactions that challenge traditional notions of morality. Without digital literacy and guided online behaviour, children may adopt inappropriate language, deception, or exclusionary behaviour in online settings (Jain, 2021).

The dynamic between school culture and moral behaviour among primary school pupils is foundational in shaping children's ethical development and social functioning. School culture embodies the collective attitudes, values, traditions, and behavioral behavioural expectations that permeate the school environment. This cultural backdrop provides the context within which young learners observe,

internalize internalise, and practice moral behaviours such as honesty, respect, cooperation, and responsibility (Thapa et al., 2023). In primary schools, a nurturing and positive culture fosters an atmosphere where moral virtues are actively taught and reinforced. When schools establish norms that prioritize prioritise kindness, fairness, and mutual respect, pupils tend to mirror these values in their interactions both inside and outside the classroom. For example, consistent reinforcement of respectful communication and empathy by teachers cultivates pupils' ability to resolve conflicts peacefully and show consideration for others' feelings (Osakwe & Edeh, 2022). This highlights how everyday social practices embedded in school culture become mechanisms for moral learning.

School culture's influence on moral behaviours is further enhanced when it integrates culturally relevant content. Egwuonwu and Obasi (2022) emphasized emphasised that embedding indigenous proverbs, folktales, and communal values into daily lessons creates meaningful connections for pupils. This culturally responsive approach validates pupils' backgrounds while reinforcing moral principles that resonate within their broader social contexts. Such integration helps bridge school and home values, resulting in a more consistent moral upbringing. Conversely, a fragmented or negative school culture, characterized characterised by unclear expectations, inconsistent discipline, or a lack of adult modeling modelling, can impede moral development. Jain (2021) opined that such environments may foster confusion or disregard for moral norms, resulting in increased behavioural problems and diminished peer cooperation. This underscores the critical need for intentional cultivation of a positive moral culture.

Albert Bandura's social learning theory posited that human behaviour, including moral conduct, is learned through observation, imitation, and modelling within social contexts. In the school setting, pupils observe and internalize behavioural norms by watching teachers, peers, and school leaders. A positive school culture that models honesty, respect, cooperation, and fairness can therefore foster similar traits among pupils. Conversely, a school culture characterized by favoritism, aggression, or indiscipline may reinforce undesirable moral behaviours. Teachers, through consistent demonstration of ethical conduct, serve as moral exemplars whose actions often speak louder than words. Reinforcement mechanisms such as praise, awards, and disciplinary measures further strengthen moral learning through consequences and expectations within the school culture (Ormrod, 2020). In primary schools, pupils' moral formation is particularly sensitive to social cues. Thus, classroom norms, peer interactions, and school-wide traditions, such as assemblies, moral instruction sessions, and community service, all provide models of appropriate moral behaviour within a shared school culture.

In essence, the relationship between school culture and moral behaviour among primary school pupils is mutually reinforcing. A positive culture provides the conditions for pupils to learn, practice, and internalize internalise moral values, while the moral behaviours exhibited by pupils contribute to sustaining and enriching that culture. For primary schools aiming to develop well-rounded, ethical citizens, deliberate attention to cultivating a values-based culture is essential. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the role of school culture in shaping moral behaviour among primary schools in Osun Central Senatorial District, Osun State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The role of school culture in shaping moral behaviour among primary school pupils has become a critical area of concern, especially in Osun State, where rapid social changes and modernization modernisation have influenced children's value systems. Despite the crucial role schools play as environments for socialization socialisation and character formation, many primary schools in Osun State Osun State face challenges in fostering a positive culture that effectively promotes moral values such as honesty, respect, responsibility, and empathy among pupils. Recent reports indicate a rise in indiscipline, bullying, and lack of respect for authority among pupils, which points to a possible decline or inadequacy in the prevailing school culture to nurture desirable moral behaviour (Akinyemi, 2021; Oladipo & Adeyemi, 2023).

While school culture encompasses shared beliefs, traditions, rituals, and norms that influence behaviour, there is limited empirical evidence on how these elements specifically impact moral development in the primary school context within Osun State. The gap in understanding the mechanisms through which school culture shapes pupils' ethical conduct has made it difficult for educators and policymakers to design effective interventions aimed at reinforcing moral behaviour. Additionally, variations in school culture across urban and rural schools, public and private institutions, and differences in leadership styles further complicate the issue, making it unclear which cultural practices most effectively promote positive moral outcomes (Ogunlade & Alabi, 2022). This problem is compounded by the interplay between home, community, and school environments, where inconsistent value systems may create conflicting messages for pupils, hindering their moral development (Adeleke, 2020). Consequently, there is a pressing need to investigate the role of school culture in shaping

the moral behaviour of primary school pupils in Osun State.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to examine the role of school culture in shaping moral behaviour among primary schools in Osun State. The study therefore sought to:

1. Examine the forms of school culture practised in primary schools in Osun State.
2. Investigate whether the school culture influences the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State.
3. Find out the specific elements of school culture that mostly contribute to shaping moral behavior among primary school in Osun State.
4. Explore the challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development in Osun State.
5. Examine how school culture can be improved to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils in Osun State.

Research Questions

The following question was answered:

1. What are the forms of school culture practised in primary schools in Osun State?
2. To what extent does the school culture influence the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State?
3. What specific elements of school culture mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour among primary school pupils in Osun State?
4. What are the challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development in Osun State?
5. What are the ways to improve school culture to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils in Osun State?

Methodology

The study focused on the role of school culture in shaping moral behaviour among primary schools in Osun State. It employed a descriptive survey research design where the opinions of the participants were sought for the research. This research design was selected because this study intends to check the role played by the school culture in shaping moral behaviour among primary school pupils in Osun State. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)(www.osunstate.gov.ng/mtss-2020-2022/), there exist 1,937 primary schools in Osun State with a total of 35,117 teachers. There are 3 Senatorial Districts in Osun State with 10 LGAs in each zone, which are Osun East, Osun West, and Osun Central. The study focused on the teachers across all the primary schools as the study population. A sample of 500 teachers were sampled across the 3 Senatorial Districts, where 170 teachers from West, 160 teachers from East, and 170 teachers from Central were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Thus, a total sample of 500 teachers from both private and public primary schools was selected as the participants for the study.

The instrument used for this research work was a self-constructed questionnaire titled “Role of School Culture in Shaping Moral Behaviour Questionnaire” (RSCMBQ). The questionnaire was close closed-ended, comprising of Sections A, and B. The section A comprises of demographic information of the respondents which are gender, school type, and years of experience; while section B, which is divided into 5 sub-sections comprised 5 items each on the forms of school culture practiced in primary schools, the school culture and moral values development in pupils, specific elements of school culture mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour, the challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development, and how school

culture can be improved to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils in OsunState. A four Likert scale was used as the response format for the instrument, which are includes SA-Strongly Agree (4 points), A-Agree (3 points), D-Disagree (2 points), and SD-Strongly Disagree (1 point).To get the cut-off mark, the average of the total points was calculated to be 2.5 (That is;, $4+3+2+1 = 10$: $10/4 = 2.5$).

The research instrument was validated by the experts in the field of Primary Education and Educational Psychology, while instrument reliability was established using Cronbach’s Alpha reliability estimate, which yielded a value To find Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the forms of school culture practised in primary schools

of 0.88. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions raised.

Results

The data collected were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 23.0). The results of the findings are shown below:

Research Questions

Five research questions were raised and answered with the use of mean and standard deviation.

Research Question One: What are the forms of school culture practiced in primary schools in Osun State?

S/N	ITEMS	X̄	SD	Remark	Rank
1.	Establishment of clear rules and routines to promote discipline and respect	2.69	1.06	Agreed	1 st
2.	Daily or weekly morning assemblies including prayers, songs, and moral lessons	2.65	1.11	Agreed	3 rd
3.	Use of storytelling, proverbs, and cultural narratives to teach values	2.63	1.14	Agreed	4 th
4.	Promotion of inclusiveness and respect for diversity within the classroom	2.67	1.08	Agreed	2 nd
5.	Implementation of social and emotional learning (SEL) programs	2.61	1.17	Agreed	5 th
Weighted Mean		2.65			

Table 1 above revealed the forms of school culture practised in primary schools in Osun State. The evidence from the respondents was seen in the table where the mean value of all the items was greater than 2.50. From their response, it was revealed that primary schools established clear rules and routines to promote discipline and respect, promote inclusiveness and respect for diversity within the classroom, maintain daily or weekly morning assemblies including prayers, songs, and moral lessons, use storytelling, proverbs, and implement social and emotional learning (SEL) programs. This was ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th, respectively, in accordance

with their mean values in the table. The overall weighted mean value of 2.65, which is greater than the cut-off mean of 2.50, indicated that most forms of school culture practised in primary schools in Osun State are settings of clear rules and routines to promote discipline and respect, and promote inclusiveness and respect for diversity within the classroom.

Research Question Two:*To what extent does the school culture influence the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation showing extent to which school culture influence the development of moral values in primary school pupils

S/N	ITEMS	X̄	SD	Remark	Rank
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1.	School culture provides pupils with clear expectations for right and wrong behaviour.	2.64	1.13	Agreed	2 nd
2.	School routines and rules promote discipline, fairness, and responsibility.	2.68	1.02	Agreed	1 st
3.	Morning assemblies and classroom discussions reinforce moral lessons and values.	2.62	1.08	Agreed	3 rd
4.	Peer interactions in a respectful school environment encourage empathy and cooperation	2.59	1.13	Agreed	5 th
5.	Social and emotional learning (SEL) programs help pupils develop self-control and ethical decision-making	2.61	1.05	Agreed	4 th
Weighted Mean		2.63			

Table 2 above revealed the extent to which school culture influence the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State. The evidence from the teachers was seen in the table, where the mean value of all the items was greater than 2.50. From their response, it was revealed that school routines and rules promote discipline, fairness, and responsibility, school culture provides pupils with clear expectations for right and wrong behaviour, morning assemblies and classroom discussions reinforce moral lessons and values, social and

emotional learning programs help pupils develop self-control and ethical decision-making, and peer interactions in a respectful school environment encourage empathy and cooperation. This was ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th respectively, in accordance with their mean values in the table. The overall mean value of **2.63**, which is greater than the cut-off mean of 2.50, indicated that school culture influences the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State.

Research Question Three: *What specific elements of school culture mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour among primary school pupils in Osun State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the specific elements of school culture that mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour among primary school pupils

S/N	ITEMS	X	SD	Remark	Rank
1.	Clear and consistent school values and codes of conduct	2.61	1.11	Agreed	3 rd
2.	Teacher role modeling of moral behaviour	2.57	1.19	Agreed	5 th
3.	Positive teacher-pupil relationships based on respect and trust	2.59	1.14	Agreed	4 th
4.	Regular moral and character education activities (assemblies, storytelling)	2.67	1.10	Agreed	1 st
5.	School rituals and traditions that reinforce moral lessons	2.63	1.11	Disagreed	2 nd
Weighted Mean		2.61			

Table 3 above shows the specific elements of school culture that mostly contribute to shaping moral behavior among primary school pupils in Osun State. The evidence from the teachers was seen in the table where the mean value of all the items were greater than 2.5. From their response, it was revealed that the specific elements of school culture that mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour are; regular moral and character education activities, school rituals and traditions that reinforce moral lessons, clear and consistent school values and codes of conduct, positive

teacher-pupil relationships based on respect and trust, and teacher role modeling of moral behaviour. These were all ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th respectively, in accordance with their mean values as revealed in table 3. The overall mean value of **2.61**, which is greater than the cut-off means of 2.50, indicated the specific elements of school culture that mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour are: regular moral and character education activities, as well as school rituals and traditions that reinforce moral lessons.

Research Question Four: *What are the challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development in Osun State?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation showing the challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development

S/N	ITEMS	X	SD	Remark	Rank
1.	Inconsistent enforcement of school rules and values by staff	2.66	1.06	Agreed	1 st
2.	Lack of moral role models among teachers or school leaders	2.59	1.17	Agreed	4 th
3.	Limited training for teachers on character education and value-based teaching	2.63	1.14	Agreed	2 nd
4.	Inadequate integration of moral education into the school curriculum	2.60	1.08	Agreed	3 rd
5.	Exposure of pupils to inappropriate content through media and technology	2.57	1.11	Agreed	5 th
Weighted Mean		2.61			

Table 4 above revealed the challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development in Osun State. The evidence from the respondents was seen in the table where the mean value of all the items was greater than 2.50. From their response, it was revealed that primary schools are faced with; inconsistent enforcement of school rules and values by staff, limited training for teachers on character education and value-based teaching, inadequate integration of moral education into the school curriculum, lack of moral role models among teachers or school leaders, and exposure of pupils to inappropriate content through media

and technology. This was ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th, respectively, in accordance with their mean values in the table. The overall mean value of **2.61**, which is greater than the cut-off means of 2.50, indicated that most challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development in Osun State are inconsistent enforcement of school rules and values by staff, and limited training for teachers on character education and value-based teaching.

Research Question Five: *What are the ways to improve school culture to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils in Osun State?*

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation showing ways to improve school culture to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils

S/N	ITEMS	X	SD	Remark	Rank
1.	Promotion of consistent enforcement of school rules and moral expectations across all staff	2.62	1.06	Agreed	3 rd
2.	Provision of regular training for teachers on character education and moral development strategies	2.59	1.17	Agreed	5 th
3.	Integration of moral and values education into daily classroom activities and subjects	2.63	1.14	Agreed	2 nd
4.	Encouragement for teachers and school leaders to model ethical and respectful behaviour	2.65	1.08	Agreed	1 st
5.	Organise regular assemblies, storytelling sessions, and moral talks focused on values	2.60	1.11	Agreed	4 th
Weighted Mean		2.62			

Table 5 above revealed ways to improve school culture to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils in Osun State. The evidence from the respondents was seen in the

table where the mean value of all the items was greater than 2.50. From their response, for school culture to be improved to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils, schools should; encourage teachers and school leaders to model ethical and respectful behaviour, integrate moral and values education into daily classroom activities and subjects,

promote consistent enforcement of school rules and moral expectations across all staff, organize regular assemblies, storytelling sessions, and provide regular training for teachers on character education and moral development strategies. This was ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th respectively, in accordance with their mean values in the table. The overall mean value of **2.62** which is greater than the cut-off means of 2.50 indicated that school culture can be improved to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils, if the schools can encourage teachers and school leaders to model ethical and respectful behaviour and integrate moral and values education into daily classroom activities and subjects.

Discussions of Findings

It was revealed from the findings of the study that the most common forms of school culture practiced in primary schools in Osun State are setting clear rules and routines to promote discipline and respect, and promoting inclusiveness and respect for diversity within the classroom. This was seen from the teachers' responses to all the items on the list, where it was confirmed that there are numerous school culture practiced in primary schools in Osun State, some of which are showed shown above. This is because school culture reflects the shared beliefs, values, customs, and day-to-day practices that shape how teaching and learning unfold. This goes in line with the submission of Thepa et al (2023), who submitted that one of the most widespread forms is the supportive or caring school culture, where emotional safety, kindness, and pupil well-being are prioritized. In this type of environment, teachers show genuine care, create welcoming classrooms, and attend to pupils' emotional and developmental needs. A supportive culture helps children feel secure, respected, and valued, which fosters the development of empathy, cooperation, and moral reasoning. They further posited that a school

might be supportive and inclusive while also maintaining a strong rule-based structure. What remains consistent is the influence of school culture in shaping pupils' attitudes, behaviours, and moral development from the early years.

More so, it was revealed from the findings that school culture influences the development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State. This was seen from the participants' responses to all the items on the list, where it was revealed that moral values development among primary school pupils is greatly influenced by the school culture. This is as a result of the fact that the culture of a school, reflected in its routines, expectations, relationships, and leadership, functions as a moral compass that subtly and consistently directs the ethical development of children. This corroborates the submission of Osakwe and Edeh (2022), who submitted that in schools with a positive and value-driven culture, children learn moral lessons not only through direct instruction but also by participating in daily rituals and social interactions. When schools emphasize values such as respect, fairness, honesty, and responsibility in their rules and practices, pupils are more likely to develop these values through consistent exposure and reinforcement. For instance, classroom rules that promote sharing and turn-taking help instill the virtue of fairness, while school-wide campaigns on kindness encourage empathy and compassion.

Furthermore, the findings above revealed that the specific elements of school culture that mostly contribute to shaping moral behaviour are regular moral and character education activities, as well as school rituals and traditions that reinforce moral lessons. This was seen from the participants' responses to all the items on the list, where it was affirmed that most of the school culture contributed to the shaping of moral behaviour among primary school pupils in the

study area. This is because while many components contribute to the broader school environment, certain specific elements have the most profound influence on how children develop and display moral character in school settings. This was supported by the assertion of Al-Mahdy and Mogamed (2022), who affirmed that one of the most significant elements is teacher role modelling. In early schooling, children observe teachers closely and often imitate their actions and attitudes. When teachers demonstrate respect, fairness, kindness, and patience in their interactions with pupils and colleagues, they send strong, non-verbal messages about how to treat others. They further posited that the ethical conduct of teachers contributes directly to the moral tone of the school, reinforcing the values pupils are expected to adopt.

Also, it was gathered from the studies that the most challenges faced by the schools in fostering a positive school culture that supports moral development in Osun State are inconsistent enforcement of school rules and values by staff, and limited training for teachers on character education and value-based teaching. This was seen from the teachers' responses to all the items on the list, where it was revealed that despite the significance of school culture in shaping the moral behaviour among pupils, its implementation is faced with numerous challenges which impede its positive implementation. This goes in line with the assertion of Al-Mahdy and Mogamed (2022), who reported that creating and sustaining a positive school culture that nurtures moral development among primary school pupils is a vital but complex task. While many schools recognise the importance of instilling values such as respect, honesty, empathy, and responsibility, they often encounter a range of challenges that hinder their efforts. These challenges are rooted in institutional limitations,

socio-cultural factors, and inconsistencies in the educational process. They further posited that a key challenge lies in the inconsistent modelling of moral behaviour by teachers and school leaders. When school staff do not consistently embody the values they seek to instill such as stress, lack of training, or personal attitudes, pupils may receive mixed messages about expected behaviour.

Additionally, it was revealed from the findings that school culture can be improved to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils if the schools can encourage teachers and school leaders to model ethical and respectful behaviour, and integrate moral and values education into daily classroom activities and subjects. This was seen from the teachers' responses to all the items on the list, where it was noted that for school culture to be improved to better support the moral behaviour of primary school pupils, certain strategies must be put in place within and outside the school premises. This corroborates the submission of Narvaez (2021), who posited that a positive and value-driven school culture plays a fundamental role in nurturing the moral behaviour of primary school pupils. However, to maximize its impact, schools must adopt deliberate strategies to strengthen their cultural environment. Improving school culture in ways that promote ethical development requires a blend of institutional commitment, teacher empowerment, value-based curricula, and inclusive community engagement.

Conclusion

It was concluded from the findings of the study that, the most forms of school culture practiced in primary schools in Osun State are setting of clear rules and routines and promotion of discipline and respect, and promote inclusiveness and respect for diversity within the classroom. Also, school culture influences the

development of moral values in primary school pupils in Osun State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following suggestions are hereby proffered:

1. School management should encourage teachers and school leaders to consistently model positive moral behaviour.
2. School management should integrate character and moral education into daily classroom instruction across subjects.
3. School management should develop and maintain clear school rules and behavioural expectations rooted in shared values.
4. School management should promote inclusive and respectful classroom environments that support empathy and fairness. School management should strengthen collaboration between schools and parents to ensure consistent moral guidance at home and school.

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